

LLMs for Model-driven Engineering: A Survey

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Abstract

Model-Driven Engineering (MDE) supports the development of large-scale, complex systems through abstraction, automation, and traceability. The rise of Large Language Models (LLMs) has renewed interest in reshaping MDE, with recent studies exploring their use in tasks such as model generation, model comprehension, as well as model to code and test generation. While early results suggest improved productivity and lower barriers to modeling, their overall impact remains unclear. To address this, we conduct a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) and analyze 228 primary studies. We examine MDE tasks addressed, how LLMs were leveraged, evaluation practices, and the availability of tools and datasets. Results indicate a rapidly growing research trend, covering 24 types of MDE tasks, with model generation as the dominant focus. Domain-Specific Languages (DSL), Unified Modeling Language (UML), and Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) are the most frequently targeted formalisms. GPT-family models and zero-shot prompting are most commonly used, with fine-tuning and retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) as typical enhancement techniques. Evaluations primarily emphasize correctness, with limited benchmarking in realistic settings and insufficiently comprehensive replication materials.

Keywords: Model-driven Engineering (MDE), Systematic Literature Review, Large-language Model (LLM)

1 Introduction

Model-Driven Engineering (MDE) has been a cornerstone of Software Engineering (SE) research and practice for over two decades, offering methodologies, tools and standards to manage the complexity of developing large-scale software systems through modeling, abstraction and automation [150, 51]. Initially driven by the vision of seamless model-to-code generation [118], Model-based Testing (MBT) [77, 270, 241, 270], and other model-enabled engineering tasks [47, 181, 267, 271], MDE fostered a rich ecosystem of Domain-specific Modeling (DSM) languages (e.g., Modelica [245]), transformation engines (e.g., ATL [128]), and validation and verification tools (e.g., Alloy [125]) that continue to serve as essential building blocks used by both practitioners and researchers, especially for developing large-scale software systems such as Cyber-physical Systems (CPS) [261, 179]. Even in the era of Artificial Intelligence (AI), MDE remains critical, as it can be considered an effective method in providing the structure and governance necessary to leverage AI-generated artifacts responsibly. While fully black-box generation may appear appealing, MDE ensures transparency, verifiability, and control, which are the qualities that black-box approaches alone cannot guarantee [197].

More than a decade ago, researchers began exploring ambitious frontiers: attempting to derive design models, source code, and test cases directly from natural language (NL) requirements [267, 268, 82, 205, 211]. During the following years, classical Machine Learning (ML) techniques (e.g., K-means clustering) were increasingly integrated into MDE workflows in an effort to address some of the limitations of earlier rule-based and manual approaches. Supervised learning models were applied to tasks such as model classification [219] and traceability link recovery [164]; clustering algorithms supported model comparison and analysis [27]; and statistical NLP pipelines were used to map textual requirements to modeling constructs [264]. While these methods occasionally reduced manual effort and development costs, their effectiveness was often inconsistent and highly dependent on the quality and availability of labelled data [51]. Consequently, the broader success of classical ML in delivering cost-effective MDE remains questionable, with results often limited to small-scale and well-controlled scenarios rather than real-world engineering practice [163].

The advent of Large Language Models (LLMs) has revived interest in revolutionizing MDE. In recent years, the MDE community has actively explored how LLMs can augment or even transform traditional modeling practices, ranging from generating domain-specific models from natural language [144, 127], synthesizing model transformations [166, 112], and analyzing model consistency [236], to producing code and test suites aligned with

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high-level specifications [89, 67]. Early findings are promising, suggesting that LLMs can lower the barrier to model creation and enhance developer productivity through automation. However, the extent of these benefits remains largely unknown.

To this end, we conduct a Systematic Literature Review (SLR) and identify 228 primary studies through a rigorous selection process. This SLR investigates which MDE tasks have been addressed across which SE activities, how LLMs have been leveraged and integrated into MDE solutions, how empirical evaluations have been conducted, and what tools and datasets are available. Our findings reveal a rapidly growing research trend, with a strong focus on model generation, widespread reliance on GPT-family models and zero-shot prompting, and with fine-tuning and retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) as typical enhancement techniques. We also observe that evaluation practices remain largely centered on correctness, with evaluation subjects predominantly limited to controlled academic settings and limited availability of publicly accessible replication materials.

Compared with existing surveys and reviews, this study provides a more comprehensive and up-to-date analysis, covering a substantially larger set of primary studies. It systematically collects and categorizes evaluation metrics, classifies LLM enhancement techniques, identifies 24 distinct MDE tasks, and analyzes commonly used types of baselines, as well as the availability of replication repositories. We believe these findings offer a valuable reference for future research and development in this area. For replicability and reproducibility, we have the artifacts of our SLR available at <https://github.com/WSE-Lab/LLM4MDE>.

Structure. Section 2 describes the research methodology. Section 3 presents the bibliometric analysis results. Section 4 presents the application landscape. Section 5 presents the analysis of proposed LLM-based MDE solutions. Section 6 discusses evaluation practices. Section 7 discusses threats to validity. Section 8 reviews the related work. Finally, Section 9 concludes the paper.

2 Research Method

In this section, we present the research method we followed to conduct this SLR.

2.1 Research Questions

To understand and investigate current research in leveraging LLMs for MDE, we carried out the survey to answer the following 15 RQs from four aspects:

- Bibliometric Analysis
 - **RQ1:** How many primary studies have been published over the years?
 - **RQ2:** What are the publication venues of all primary studies?
 - **RQ3:** What types of publications do the primary studies belong?
- Application Landscape
 - **RQ4:** What types of MDE tasks are tackled by LLM-based MDE solutions?
 - **RQ5:** What SE activities are addressed by LLM-based MDE solutions?
 - **RQ6:** Which modeling languages and model types do LLM-based MDE solutions cover?
 - **RQ7:** Which application domains do LLM-based MDE solutions target?
- Proposed Solutions
 - **RQ8:** What foundation models are used in LLM-based MDE solutions?
 - **RQ9:** How are prompt engineering techniques used in LLM-based MDE solutions?
 - **RQ10:** How are LLMs enhanced?
 - **RQ11:** How are LLMs integrated with traditional MDE tools and platforms?
 - **RQ12:** In what ways are humans involved in the loop of LLM-based MDE solutions?
- Evaluation Practices
 - **RQ13:** What metrics are used to evaluate the LLM-based MDE solutions?
 - **RQ14:** What baselines were used to assess LLM-based MDE solutions?
 - **RQ15:** What public replication artifacts do the primary studies provide?

Answering these RQs involves a comprehensive and systematic examination of the literature on applying LLMs to MDE. We begin with a bibliometric analysis, followed by an overview of the MDE tasks addressed in the primary studies. Next, we analyze each solution in terms of the foundation models used, the prompt engineering techniques applied, etc. We also report on the evaluation practices, the availability of replication packages, etc.

Figure 1: The process of collecting the primary studies

2.2 Databases and Search Queries

We employed five databases for the SLR: ACM, IEEEExplore, Scopus, Springer Nature Link, and Web of Science (WoS). These databases were selected because they are commonly used in SLR studies in SE and provide broad coverage of relevant literature.

To investigate recent advances in applying LLMs to MDE, hereafter referred to as LLM-based MDE, we define two sets of search terms, as shown in Listing 1. The first set comprises of MDE-related keywords (e.g., “system modeling”, “DSM”, “Simulink”) and is designed to capture relevant MDE literature. The second set consists of LLM-related terms, adapted from existing literature reviews on LLMs [122, 146, 255].

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("system modeling" OR "software modeling" OR "domain modeling" OR "model-driven engineering"
OR "model driven engineering" OR "MDE" OR "model-based software engineering" OR "model-
based system engineering" OR "model based software engineering" OR "model based system
engineering" OR "MBSE" OR "model-based engineering" OR "model based engineering" OR "MBE"
OR "model-based testing" OR "model based testing" OR "MBT" OR "domain-specific modeling"
OR "DSM" OR "MDD" OR "MDA" OR "model-driven architecture" OR "model driven architecture"
OR "model-driven development" OR "model driven development" OR "UML" OR "SysML" OR "OCL"
OR "BPMN" OR "Simulink" OR "DSL" OR "DSML") AND
("LLM" OR "LLMs" OR "Large Language Model" OR "Large Language Models" OR "Language Model" OR "
Language Models" OR "Large Model" OR "Large Models" OR "LM" OR "Generative Language Model"
OR "Generative Language Models" OR "Generative Model" OR "Generative Models" OR "
Generative AI" OR "GAI" OR "Artificial General Intelligence" OR "AGI" OR "GPT" OR "BERT"
OR "T5" OR "Gemini" OR "Llama" OR "Claude" OR "DeepSeek" OR "Grok" OR "Qwen" OR "PaLM")

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Listing 1: Search Queries

2.3 Paper Selection

The process of deriving the 228 primary studies is illustrated in Figure 1. The figure marks the number of papers we collected after each phase. We conducted the initial search with the defined search strings on five databases on 16-Jun-2025 and obtained 2728 papers published from 2017 and 2025. After removing duplicates, we further applied the inclusion and exclusion criteria (Table 1) and eventually obtained the initial set of primary studies, which has 122 papers. The inclusion and exclusion criteria are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

#	Inclusion and Exclusion Criterion
1	The paper is written in English.
2	The paper must address SE activities.
3	The paper must tackle specific MDE tasks or support MDE by addressing upstream tasks.
4	The paper must propose an LLM-based method, vision, or a benchmarking study of LLM-based approaches.
6	The paper is not a book, erratum, data paper, note, editorial or letter.
7	The paper is not a survey or a systematic literature review.
8	The paper is not published in doctoral symposium.

To be inclusive, after performing database searches with the defined search strings, we also conducted snowballing. From the 122 initially selected studies, on 31-Oct-2025, we systematically performed both backward and forward snowballing, terminating the process when no additional relevant publications could be identified. During this process, we applied the paper selection criteria listed in Table 1. Three authors of this paper engaged in intensive discussions throughout the entire process and reached a consensus on the final selections. As a result of the forward and backward snowballing, we obtained $80+26=106$ additional papers. Combined with the the 122 publications identified through the database search, we finally formed a pool of 228 primary studies.

2.4 Data Extraction

At the beginning of the process of extracting data from the primary studies to answer the RQs, we created an spreadsheet including metadata such as the title, publication year, and venue, of all 228 papers. To systematically extract additional data, we defined the information to be extracted for each RQ, as shown in Table 2, based on which we refined the spreadsheet with additional columns. RQ1 and RQ2 can be directly answered by the metadata directly obtained from the databases. To answer RQ3-RQ16, we reviewed each primary study in detail to extract required information. The process is naturally iterative as continuous cross-checking and comparison among studies helped ensure consistency and reliability in data extraction. For replicability and reproducibility, we have the initial search results and extracted data of selected primary studies available at <https://github.com/WSE-Lab/LLM4MDE>.

Table 2: Information collection for answering each RQ

RQs	Information to be collected
RQ1	Publication year of each primary study
RQ2	Publication venue of each primary study
RQ3	1) Publication type (e.g., conference, journal) of each primary study 2) Paper type (e.g., proposed method, new idea or vision) of each primary study
RQ4	Type(s) of MDE tasks tackled in each primary study
RQ5	1) Type(s) of SE activities addressed in each primary study 2) Type(s) of SE tasks addressed in each primary study
RQ6	1) Modeling language(s) (e.g., SysML, UML) manipulated in each primary study 2) Specific model type(s) (e.g., class diagram, state machine) and category(ies) (e.g., structural, behavioral) concerned in each primary study
RQ7	Application domain(s) (e.g., transportation) concerned in each primary study
RQ8	Foundation LLM family(ies) (e.g., LLaMA) used in each LLM-based MDE solution
RQ9	Prompt engineering technique(s) (e.g., chain-of-thought) employed in each LLM-based MDE solution
RQ10	LLM enhancement technique(s) (e.g., fine-tuning, RAG) applied in each LLM-based MDE solution
RQ11	MDE tool(s) and platform(s) integrated or supported in each LLM-based MDE solution
RQ12	Patterns of human-in-the-loop involvement in each LLM-based MDE solution
RQ13	1) Effectiveness metric(s) applied in evaluating each LLM-based MDE solution 2) Cost metric(s) applied in evaluating each LLM-based MDE solution
RQ14	1) Baseline approach(es) selected in each LLM-based MDE solution 2) Type of each baseline approach
RQ15	1) Replicable artifact(s) (e.g., code, evaluation subject) provided in each primary study 2) Hyperlinks of all replicable artifacts

3 Bibliometric Analysis

This section presents the bibliometric analysis of the comprehensive set of 228 primary studies.

3.1 RQ1: How many primary studies have been published over the years?

As shown in Figure 2, the use of LLMs for MDE has increased dramatically in recent years, as expected, particularly from 2023 to Oct-2025. This likely reflects a growing research interest in applying LLMs to MDE, and more broadly, to SE.

3.2 RQ2: What are the publication venues of all primary studies?

We summarize the venues that have three and more primary studies included in Table 3. The table reveals a high degree of diversity in publication venues: 108 primary studies appeared in distinct conferences, 30 in different journals, and 17 in various workshops. It is no surprise that the International Conference on Model Driven Engineering Languages and Systems (MODELS) and its companion Proceedings (MODELS-Companion) attracted in total $9 + 12 = 21$ primary studies, giving its strong focus on MDE. Considering that the International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE) and the International Conference on Conceptual Modeling (ER) focus on requirements modeling and conceptual modeling, which are the areas well within the scope of MDE, they attracted 7 (REW) and 9 primary studies, respectively. Similarly, the journal Software and Systems Modeling (SoSyM), which is dedicated exclusively to MDE, also attracted 6 studies. Additionally, specialized

Figure 2: Number of publications over the years

Table 3: Number of publications per venue

Venue	#Papers	Venue Type
1 <i>Other Conference</i>	108	Conference
2 <i>Other Journal</i>	30	Journal
3 <i>Other Workshop</i>	17	Workshop
4 <i>International Conference on Model Driven Engineering Languages and Systems (MODELS): Companion Proceedings</i>	12	Workshop
5 <i>International Conference on Conceptual Modeling (ER)</i>	9	Conference
6 <i>International Conference on Model Driven Engineering Languages and Systems (MODELS)</i>	9	Conference
7 <i>International Requirements Engineering Conference (RE) Workshops</i>	7	Workshop
8 <i>Software and Systems Modeling (SoSyM)</i>	6	Journal
9 <i>International Conference on Cooperative Information Systems (CoopIS)</i>	5	Conference
10 <i>Business Process Management (BPM) Workshops</i>	4	Workshop
11 <i>Enterprise, Business-Process and Information Systems Modeling (BPMDS, EMMSAD)</i>	4	Conference
12 <i>International Conference on Model-Based Software and Systems Engineering (MODELSWARD)</i>	4	Conference
13 <i>International Conference on Process Mining (ICPM) Workshops</i>	4	Workshop
14 <i>Euromicro Conference on Software Engineering and Advanced Applications (SEAA)</i>	3	Conference
15 <i>IEEE Access</i>	3	Journal
16 <i>International Conference on Software Architecture Companion (SAC)</i>	3	Workshop

venues focusing on business process modeling, system modeling, software architecture, etc. also attracted 3–4 primary studies each.

3.3 RQ3: What types of publications do the primary studies belong?

We classify the publication venues of all 228 primary studies into three categories: conference, journal and workshops. The counts of these categories are provided in Figure 3, which shows that 144 out of 228 were published in conferences, 45 in workshops and 39 in journals. While most studies appear in conferences and workshops, which is typical in software engineering, the relatively high number of workshop publications may suggest ongoing exploratory efforts.

We further examine the types of papers published, as shown in Figure 3: 153 primary studies (67.11%) propose methods, while 15 (6.58%) present new ideas or vision papers, 56 (24.56%) report benchmarks and evaluations, and 4 (1.75%) are tool demonstration papers. This distribution indicates that our dataset is strongly method-centric: more than two-thirds of the primary studies introduce explicit methodological contributions. Consequently, the corpus is appropriate for a systematic analysis of methodological approaches.

Paper Type	Total Count	Percentage
Proposed method	153	67.11%
Benchmarking and evaluation	56	24.56%
New idea or vision	15	6.58%
Tool demo	4	1.75%

Figure 3: Number of publications according to types of venue and paper.

Table 4: Definition of 24 MDE tasks

MDE Task	Definition
1 <i>Model Generation</i>	Construct models/metamodels from higher-level artifacts, e.g., requirements
2 <i>Model Comprehension</i>	Interpret, summarize, or explain models to improve human understanding of their structures and behaviors
3 <i>Model Completion</i>	Complete partial models by inferring and suggesting model elements
4 <i>Model Analysis</i>	Evaluate models in terms of completeness, consistency, correctness, etc.
5 <i>Model-based Code Generation</i>	Generate code in targeted programming languages from models
6 <i>Model-based Test Generation</i>	Generate tests from models
7 <i>Model Transformation</i>	Transform models across different abstraction levels or modeling languages
8 <i>Model Element Extraction</i>	Extract model elements from higher-level artifacts or generate relevant elements for a given context
9 <i>Model Restructuring</i>	Refactoring models to support a specific purpose
10 <i>Model Matching</i>	Identify alignments between elements of different models
11 <i>Model Constraint Generation</i>	Generate model constraints in formal languages such as OCL
12 <i>Model-driven Reverse Engineering</i>	Construct models from lower-level artifacts such as source code
13 <i>Model-based Code Evolution</i>	Evolve code in response to changes in corresponding models/metamodels
14 <i>Model Synthesis</i>	Generate synthetic models to support data construction, benchmarking, etc.
15 <i>Model Query Generation</i>	Generate queries in formal languages from NL specifications to retrieve relevant model instances
16 <i>Model Operation</i>	Generate traces of modeling operations that construct a given model compliant with a specific metamodel
17 <i>Model Evolution</i>	Evolve models in response to changes in metamodels or related artifacts such as requirements
18 <i>Model-based Test Execution</i>	Execute tests from NL instructions based on models
19 <i>Model-based Code Completion</i>	Complete partial code based on models
20 <i>Model View Generation</i>	Generate model view definitions
21 <i>Model Slicing</i>	Slice models into subsets relevant to specific requirements
22 <i>Model Recognition</i>	Identify models from images, etc.
23 <i>Model Mutation</i>	Generate model mutants from seed models according to metamodels and mutation specifications
24 <i>Model Classification</i>	Categorize models or model elements for a specific purpose

Key Finding on Bibliometric Analysis

Publications in this area have increased dramatically in recent years. The venues are highly diverse, with conferences such as MODELS, RE, and ER, as well as the journal SoSyM, each attracting more than 5 primary studies. Overall, the majority of the primary studies appear in conferences and workshops.

4 Landscape of LLM-based MDE Solutions

To investigate LLM-based solutions, this section presents our analysis based on 153 primary studies that propose new solutions, excluding studies of other types (see Figure 3).

4.1 RQ4: What types of MDE tasks are tackled by LLM-based MDE solutions?

By analyzing 153 primary studies, we identified, in total, **24 types of MDE tasks** addressed by the LLM-based solutions. The definition of each type of tasks is provided in Table 4. Compared to existing surveys [85, 51, 163], our analysis identifies 12 additional types of MDE tasks, i.e., model comprehension, model-based test generation, model element extraction, model constraint generation, model-based code evolution, model synthesis, model query generation, model operation, model-based code completion, model view generation, model slicing, and model mutation.

We plot the distribution of the MDE tasks being tackled by the primary studies in Figure 4. The figure clearly shows that model generation is the most targeted task, attracting 89 primary studies, followed by model comprehension with 12 studies, and model completion as well as model analysis as the third most common tasks, each with 9 studies. This focus on model generation is unsurprising, as MDE relies on explicit knowledge models (e.g., UML state machines) whose manual construction has long been a major bottleneck in practice; consequently, automated model generation, through approaches like rule-based model generation from requirements [82, 266], has been a key enabler of MDE over the past decade, and the community is now exploring whether LLMs can help overcome this persistent challenge. The attention given to model comprehension likely due to the success of LLMs in understanding and reasoning over textual content [263], which inspires researchers to explore their potential for interpreting models. Similarly, model analysis has also gained increasing attention, as it goes beyond model comprehension and interpretation to support the evaluation of whether constructed models are sufficiently

Figure 4: Bar plot representing the distribution of papers across MDE Tasks

complete, consistent and correct to enable subsequent downstream tasks [257]. Model completion attracts interest likely because LLMs excel at predicting and generating missing parts of structured or semi-structured data, including tasks such as code completion [123], making them a natural fit for auto-completing partial models, which is a common requirement in iterative modeling workflows.

Model-based code generation, model-based test generation, model transformation, model element extraction, and model constraint generation received attention from 6, 5, 4, 4 and 3 primary studies, respectively. This distribution indicates a tendency of to apply LLMs to derive downstream artifacts (e.g., code or test cases) from models, or to synthesize fine-grained modeling parts (e.g., individual model elements or constraints). These activities are closely aligned with the core principles of MDE, which emphasize the systematic derivation of downstream artifacts from models to enhance automation, consistency, and development productivity [130]. Moreover, model restructuring and model matching were studied in 3 primary studies each, highlighting the potential of LLMs in automating model refactoring, etc.

Considering that 89 primary studies focused on model generation, we further classify their proposed approaches into the following 10 categories: 1) standard language-based modeling, with UML, SysML, BPMN, Ecore etc.; 2) DSL development such as defining DSL’s abstract and concrete syntax, and semantics; 3) domain-specific modeling: generating domain-specific models conforming to a given DSL; 4) taxonomy construction: identifying hierarchical relations between concepts or entities to build taxonomies for a particular domain; 5) ontology learning: identifying terms, types, relations, and potentially axioms from textual information to generate ontology; 6) formal process modeling: generating formally-defined process models such as Petri Nets; 7) enterprise modeling: modeling the structure, processes, information and resources of a business, government body, or other organizations; 8) data modeling: generating models that describe the structure, relationships, and constraints of data within a system or domain [231], such as entity-relationship models; 9) goal modeling: capturing goal decomposition, resolving goal conflicts and supporting goals with evidence; and 10) causal inference: specifying cause-and-effect relationships between variables within a given system or context [117].

4.2 RQ5: What SE activities are addressed by LLM-based MDE solutions?

Since our study focuses on MDE tasks within the context of SE, we examine which SE problems these tasks aim to address. To this end, we align our analysis with the well-established Guide to the Software Engineering Body of Knowledge (SWEBOK) [257] and classify all primary studies according to its taxonomy of SE activities. The results are summarized in Table 5.

Through this classification, we observed that, in some primary studies, the targeted SE activity can potentially span multiple phases and therefore cannot be clearly determined. For example, the primary study [46] proposes an approach for deriving domain models from user studies. However, these models can potentially support

Table 5: Papers for tackling SE problems

SE Activity	SE Task	#	Papers
SE Models And Methods	<i>N/A</i>	59	[43, 7, 166, 113, 269, 75, 53, 258, 111, 117, 103, 169, 195, 160, 87, 156, 71, 37, 127, 159, 18, 171, 39, 68, 155, 165, 21, 143, 81, 65, 254, 259, 119, 108, 41, 272, 168, 229, 74, 38, 247, 218, 25, 54, 73, 235, 191, 112, 202, 276, 6, 109, 162, 22, 99, 242, 91, 34, 141]
Unspecified Context	<i>N/A</i>	48	[194, 46, 249, 10, 226, 178, 196, 265, 126, 72, 45, 8, 153, 275, 139, 12, 4, 17, 66, 19, 144, 33, 133, 152, 121, 36, 134, 137, 35, 94, 214, 16, 184, 76, 227, 154, 161, 209, 220, 102, 50, 64, 31, 188, 151, 62, 180, 105]
Software Requirements	<i>Requirement Specification</i>	21	[262, 182, 135, 96, 213, 175, 114, 236, 244, 42, 30, 176, 206, 79, 173, 203, 273, 212, 231, 157, 13]
	<i>Requirement Analysis</i>	2	[273, 231]
	<i>Requirement Decomposition</i>	1	[274]
Software Construction	<i>Coding</i>	9	[100, 207, 175, 114, 274, 52, 192, 24, 189]
	<i>Database Construction</i>	1	[250]
Software Design	<i>Model-Based Design</i>	9	[136, 28, 175, 114, 190, 274, 24, 231, 251]
Software Testing	<i>Test Design And Implementation</i>	6	[84, 23, 172, 193, 170, 189]
	<i>Test Incident Reporting</i>	1	[158]
Software Architecture	<i>Architecture Synthesis</i>	4	[239, 246, 142, 252]
Software Maintenance	<i>Evolution Of Software</i>	2	[136, 129]
	<i>Reverse Engineering</i>	2	[224, 225]
Software Configuration Management	<i>Software Configuration Identification</i>	1	[274]
SE Management	<i>Traceability Analysis</i>	1	[136]

multiple SE activities, such as design, construction, validation and verification. In such cases, we categorize the study as *Unspecified Context*. Overall, 48 primary studies were classified into this category. One reason is that, in the context of MDE, models serve as central and reusable artifacts that can support SE activities across the development lifecycle.

Except for *Unspecified Context*, from the table, we can observe that around one-third (59) of the primary studies fall into the category of SE Models and Methods (Chapter 11 of SWEBOK [257]), which covers topics: modeling, types of models, analysis of models and SE methods. It is therefore unsurprising that this is the largest group, given the inherent alignment with MDE. Software requirements is the second largest category, with 22 primary studies focus on it, among which 21 are about requirements specification (through modeling), 2 are about requirements analysis and one is about requirements decomposition. Requirements modeling and analysis is a well-established subfield within MDE, which explains the substantial number of studies in this category. The Software Construction category includes 9 primary studies model-based code generation, and 1 study on database construction. There are 9 model-based design works (under Software Design). In the area of Software Testing, there are 7 primary studies: 6 addressing test design and implementation, and 1 focusing on test incident reporting. There are also 4 studies on software architecture synthesis (under Software Architecture). We also identified 2 papers on Reverse Engineering and 2 on Software Evolution (i.e., Software Maintenance). In addition, there is 1 primary study on Software Configuration Identification (under Software Configuration Management), and 1 on Traceability Analysis (belonging to SE Management). The trend suggests that the MDE community is heavily investing in automating forward engineering (from models to code and tests). However, we see valuable opportunities to focus on software artifact evolution, maintenance, and cross-cutting concerns like traceability, which are essential areas for the long-term development and maintenance of large-scale software systems but currently remain underrepresented.

4.3 RQ6: Which modeling languages and model types do LLM-based MDE solutions cover?

4.3.1 Modeling Languages

In MDE, identifying which modeling languages are used is essential. We summarize the modeling languages employed across the primary studies in Figure 5. DSLs form the largest group, with 48 primary studies focusing on manipulating DSL models to perform MDE tasks. As expected, UML is the second most widely adopted modeling language in the MDE tasks, appearing in 45 studies. This is unsurprising, as UML is an OMG standard with a well-established ecosystem, including mature modeling tools (e.g., Papyrus [88], MagicDraw [183]),

Figure 5: Bar plot representing the distribution of papers across each modeling language. *DSL*: Domain-specific Language; *UML*: Unified Modeling Language; *BPMN*: Business Process Model and Notation; *SysML*: System Modeling Language; *OCL*: Object Constraint Language; *4EM*: For Enterprise Modeling; *SIG*: Softgoal Interdependency Graph; *OWL*: Web Ontology Language; *GRL*: Goal-oriented Requirement Language; *FMMLx*: Flexible Multi-Level Modeling and Execution Language; *EPC*: Event-driven Process Chain; *EA*: Eliminative Argumentation.

extensive documentation, and strong community support, and enjoys broad adoption in both industry and academia (e.g., [243, 186]). Consequently, UML models are far more prevalent than those in other modeling languages, offering a relatively rich and accessible source of data that can be leveraged to train or fine-tune LLMs for MDE tasks.

The third most frequently used language is Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN), another OMG standardized graphical modeling language for specifying and analyzing business processes, and appears in requirements engineering, design and process automation. As shown in Figure 5, BPMN was used in 30 primary studies. Like UML, BPMN is an OMG standard with mature tool support (e.g., Camunda Modeler [58]) and well-defined execution semantics [1]. Its strong alignment with workflow and service-oriented systems, particularly in enterprise and process-driven contexts, makes it a natural fit for tasks such as workflow modeling and automation.

Beyond DSL, UML and BPMN, we observed 11 on Ecore models in the context of Eclipse Modeling Framework (EMF) [232], 8 on the generation of System Modeling Language (SysML v1), 6 on Object Constraint Language (OCL), and 5 on Petri Nets. Other languages, such as Declare diagrams, and various other notations, appear in only 1 or 2 primary studies each, reflecting the diversity but also the fragmentation of modeling approaches in the field.

We further illustrate the mapping between modeling languages and MDE tasks in Figure 6. It can be observed that the combination of DSLs and model generation is the most prevalent, followed by model generation with UML, and then model generation with BPMN. The combination of SysML v1 and model generation appears in 7 primary studies, while Ecore model generation is reported in 6 studies. All other combinations occur in five or fewer primary studies. DSLs cover the widest range of MDE tasks, including model generation, model mutation, and model-based test generation, among others. Similarly, UML is applied across multiple MDE tasks. For BPMN, we observe that primary studies mainly focus on model generation, model element extraction, model comprehension, model completion, and analysis. In contrast, there is little or no work on model-based testing, model transformation, model operation, or model mutation. This is expected, as BPMN is primarily designed for business process modeling, rather than for representing detailed software or system behavior, such as those captured by UML state machines or sequence diagrams.

4.3.2 Model Types

According to the classification in SWEBOK, we categorize models into structural and behavioral models. As shown in Figure 7, 63 primary studies (32.64%) address behavioral models, dominated by process models (35), followed by sequence diagrams (9), activity diagrams (7), and state machines (6). In contrast, 47 primary studies (24.35%) focus on structural models, mainly class diagrams (29). Additionally, 21 primary studies (10.88%) deal with requirements-related models, such as use cases and goal models. Seven studies address architectural

Figure 6: Heatmap illustrating the distribution of modeling languages across different types of MDE tasks

Figure 7: Bar plot representing the distribution of papers associated with each type of models

models, including component-based representations. A small number of studies focus on analysis models (3), constraints (3), and verification models (2). Additionally, DSMs, which may correspond to different model types (e.g., structural or behavioral), are grouped under others; finally, five studies do not specify model types they employed, and two are not applicable.

Overall, the distribution between structural and behavioral models is relatively balanced. For structural modeling, class diagrams dominates the category with 29 primary studies, indicating the widespread adoption of UML within the MDE community. For behavioral modeling, process models are the most common, mainly reflecting the widespread use of BPMN, which we previously identified as the third most frequently used modeling language (Figure 5). When focusing specifically on software system behavior, sequence diagrams, activity diagrams, and state machines are the most commonly used representations. For requirements modeling, use case models remain the dominant form. These observations are consistent with those from the literature even before the emergence of LLM-based approaches.

4.4 RQ7: Which application domains do LLM-based MDE solutions target?

As summarized in Table 6, most primary studies (129) do not restrict their approaches to a specific application domain. Among the domain-specific studies, 8 target computing and digital systems (e.g., CPS and embedded systems), 5 address transportation systems (e.g., autonomous driving systems), 4 focus on aerospace and space technologies, and 4 study educational systems. In addition, one study addresses crisis management systems, one focuses on public administration, and one investigates energy and power systems.

These results indicate a strong emphasis on domain-agnostic MDE methods, tools, and frameworks intended for cross-domain applicability. This pattern may also reflect the predominance of early-stage research, which tends to prioritize methodological innovation over extensive domain-specific validation. When particular domains are addressed, MDE is most frequently applied to safety-critical and highly complex software-intensive systems, such as CPS and IoT systems, where modeling practices are already deeply embedded in industrial workflows

Table 6: Applications domains of LLM-based MDE solutions

Domain	#	Papers
General Systems	129	[224, 7, 100, 166, 113, 239, 136, 46, 182, 269, 10, 75, 53, 258, 135, 111, 117, 226, 178, 196, 129, 28, 207, 96, 213, 175, 195, 114, 160, 87, 265, 156, 71, 37, 126, 236, 72, 159, 45, 190, 172, 8, 274, 171, 153, 39, 275, 170, 155, 165, 139, 21, 12, 52, 252, 143, 4, 17, 66, 19, 81, 65, 250, 192, 254, 144, 259, 30, 133, 152, 121, 119, 176, 36, 108, 134, 137, 41, 272, 35, 94, 214, 229, 16, 184, 76, 79, 74, 173, 38, 247, 203, 218, 25, 225, 227, 54, 154, 209, 73, 24, 220, 212, 231, 235, 191, 112, 202, 157, 50, 64, 31, 276, 251, 6, 188, 109, 162, 13, 22, 99, 242, 62, 91, 34, 189, 180, 105, 141]
Computing and Digital Systems	8	Network [194], Smart TVs [23], Robotic Process Automation [249], CPS [169, 168], Cloud Computing [127], Enterprise Digital Twins [33], Embedded System [206]
Transportation Systems	5	ADS [84, 158, 193], Train Autonomous Control System [262],
Aerospace Systems	4	Spacecraft [246], Aircraft [142], Aerospace [244, 273]
Education Systems	4	[43, 103, 18, 102]
Governance and Public Systems	2	Crisis Management [68], Public Administration [161]
Energy and Power Systems	1	[151]

(e.g., through standards such as AUTOSAR [97] in the automotive sector).

Key Finding on the Landscape of LLM-based MDE Solutions

Model generation is the most targeted task, followed by model comprehension, completion, and analysis. Most primary studies do not focus on specific *SE phases*: about one third fall under the SWEBOK category SE Models and Methods, another one third do not specify the phase, and among the remaining studies, requirements engineering is the most frequently addressed activity. Regarding *modeling languages*, DSLs are the most targeted, followed by UML and BPMN. The most common combination is DSL + model generation, followed by UML + model generation and BPMN + model generation. The studies are roughly balanced between *structural and behavioral models*. Class diagrams dominates the structural category, while process models dominate the behavioral category. Sequence, activity, and state machine diagrams each appear in more than five studies, while use cases are the most common form of requirements modeling. Overall, the considered model types are diverse. Most studies propose *domain-agnostic MDE* methods, tools, or frameworks, emphasizing general applicability rather than domain-specific validation.

5 Proposed LLM-based MDE Solutions

To investigate LLM-based MDE solutions, this section presents our analysis based on 153 primary studies that propose concrete solutions (Figure 3).

5.1 RQ8: What foundation models are used in LLM-based MDE solutions?

Foundation models used in the primary studies are summarized in Figure 8. As shown, GPT is by far the most widely adopted, appearing in 111 studies. It is followed by LLaMA (31 studies), Mistral (13), Gemini (10), Claude and DeepSeek (9 each), and BERT (6). Numerous other foundation models were also employed, though each appeared in only one to three primary studies, reflecting the long tail of foundation model usage in the field. The overwhelming adoption of GPT likely reflects its early public availability via a user-friendly API and widespread use as a benchmark in SE research.

5.2 RQ9: How are prompt engineering techniques used in LLM-based MDE solutions?

Prompt engineering must be examined in LLM-based MDE because prompts define how transformation logic, structural constraints, and modeling rules are expressed to LLMs, which directly influence the correctness and reliability of MDE tasks. In Figure 9, we present the distribution and intersections of prompt engineering techniques used in the LLM-based MDE studies proposed in the primary studies.

The horizontal bars on the left represent the total frequency of each individual technique, which shows that ZeroShot (67), FewShot (57), Role (27), Chain-of-Thought (COT, 26) and Iterative (25), and PromptChaining (19) prompting are the most commonly adopted strategies. These are different prompting strategies where a LLM is guided by direct instructions, examples, assigned roles, iterative refinement, or step-by-step reasoning

Figure 8: Bar chart presenting the distribution of foundation models employed in the primary studies

to perform a task. ZeroShot, FewShot, and Role Prompting dominate due to their low computational cost and immediate integration into development workflows. Also, these techniques were proposed earlier than other techniques such as Tree-of-Thought (ToT), which appear less frequently in the survey because they were introduced more recently and involve significantly higher implementation overhead and token costs compared to the established foundational techniques [217].

The vertical bars indicate the sizes of specific technique combinations. The two largest bars correspond to single-technique usages (i.e., ZeroShot and FewShot), which suggests that many studies rely on individual prompting strategies. However, numerous smaller bars (with 1-5 primary studies each) demonstrate that various techniques are also combined. This indicates that the literature also made effort on experimenting hybrid prompting strategies. For instance, role prompting is combined with few-shot examples to provide both role-conditioned context and explicit structural guidance for LLM.

Overall, we observe that a field is still dominated by simple, standalone methods, with advanced frameworks like ToT remaining highly specialized and rarely combined with other techniques in the current literature.

5.3 RQ10: How are LLMs enhanced?

Investigating enhancement techniques (e.g., Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG), fine-tuning, and multi-agent systems) is critical because general-purpose LLMs often lack domain specificity, conformance to structural and schema constraints, and up-to-date technical knowledge required to reliably automate complex MDE tasks. Hence, as shown in Figure 10, we summarize the enhancement techniques employed by the primary studies. From the figure, we observe that among the 153 primary studies (Table 3), only 43 employed enhancement techniques. Within this subset, fine-tuning is the most adopted one (21), followed by RAG (16). Other techniques, i.e., multi-agent, knowledge base, pre-training, and instruction tuning, attracted significantly less attention, with 3, 2, 2, and 1 primary studies, respectively.

Concentrating on fine-tuning and RAG highlights a strategic preference for addressing the two most immediate barriers in MDE: syntactic rigor and technical accuracy. Fine-tuning adapts LLM weights to better capture patterns of formal modeling grammars, while RAG provides a cost-effective mechanism to ground outputs in external technical documentation. In contrast, the lower adoption of multi-agent systems and pre-training likely reflects the higher barriers to use, including the architectural complexity of harnessing multiple agents and the significant corpus as well as computational resources required for model pre-training. For instance, primary study [154] proposes a framework for automatically generating process models through multi-agent orchestration that combines generation, refinement, reviewing, and modification. Primary study [25] is the only one that employs instruction tuning, which is a specialized form of fine-tuning in which a pre-trained language model learns to follow natural language instructions across multiple tasks by minimizing a supervised loss function through instruction and output pairs.

Furthermore, from Figure 10, we can observe that for model generation (in red), fine-tuning (12 out of 21 studies) and RAG (9 out of 16 studies) are the dominant techniques, possibly reflecting their capabilities in addressing strict syntactic requirements and domain knowledge needed for generating valid models. A similar preference can be also observed in model comprehension, which relied exclusively on these two techniques.

Figure 9: Prompt engineering techniques employed in the primary studies

Figure 10: Enhancement techniques for each type of MDE tasks

For model mutation and model restructuring, the limited numbers of studies make it difficult to identify any meaningful trends. However, it is worth noting that knowledge base techniques were utilized only within these two niche areas. Finally, instruction tuning appears as a specialized outlier, currently applied only within the context of ontology learning, where the tuning pipeline involves multiple tasks, including term typing, type taxonomy discovery and type non-taxonomic relation extraction.

In addition, we observe four primary studies that apply more than one enhancement techniques. Primary studies [190, 39] combine fine-tuning with RAG for constructing OCL constraints and business process comprehension, respectively; primary study [31] leverages multi-agent techniques with RAG to generate instances of domain models; and primary study [151] adopts a two-stage training strategy combining pre-training and fine-tuning to integrate domain knowledge with task-specific knowledge in generating BPMN diagrams.

Moreover, Figure 11 presents the enhancement techniques combined with each LLM family. As shown, the research landscape is heavily dominated by LLaMA (owing to its open-weight architecture) and GPT (the primary high-performing option during RAG’s foundational years), which serve as the main subjects for both fine-tuning (7 and 5 papers) and RAG (6 and 7 papers). While fine-tuning remains the most ubiquitous technique across the majority of model families, RAG shows concentrated activity specifically within these two leading architectures. In contrast, other models such as Mistral and Gemini show minimal representation, with only two and one paper(s) respectively in the RAG category. Conversely, areas such as multi-agent systems and knowledge base integration represent emerging or niche segments with comparatively lower research frequency, appearing primarily in studies involving GPT and DeepSeek.

5.4 RQ11: How are LLMs integrated with traditional MDE tools and platforms?

Discussing the integration of LLMs within traditional MDE approaches and toolchains is important because it highlights how advanced LLM capabilities can enhance MDE processes, improve automation, and bridge gaps between human expertise and tool-supported development. We present the results of our survey regarding this aspect in Table 7.

As shown in Table 7, among the 72 primary studies where LLM-based MDE solutions were integrated with traditional MDE tools and platforms, PlantUML is the most frequently used tool (19 instances), predominantly for model generation (10), followed by model analysis (2) and model-based code generation (2), and with limited use (1 each) in model constraint generation, model matching, model recognition, model restructuring, model synthesis, model transformation, model view generation, and model-based code generation. The Eclipse Modeling Framework (EMF) is also frequently used (16 instances), primarily for model generation (7) and model completion (4), with additional applications in model operation (2) and limited use (1 each) in model constraint generation, model mutation, model view generation, model-based code evolution, and model-based test generation. Moreover, a significant portion of tools (PyEcore, Eclipse Sirius, Eclipse Capella, Eclipse SiDiff Web) also belongs to the EMF ecosystem.

One plausible explanation is that PlantUML and EMF are frequently used in traditional MDE: PlantUML is

Figure 11: Enhancement techniques applied on each LLM family

Table 7: Integration of LLMs with traditional MDE tools and platforms

Tool (#)	MDE Task (#)	Modeling Language (#) Papers
1 PlantUML (19)	Model generation (10)	UML (7) [194, 239, 226, 126, 274, 142, 188], DSL (2) [37, 231], Ecore (1) [194], SysML v1 (1) [136]
	Model analysis (2)	UML (2) [6, 180]
	Model-based code generation (2)	UML (2) [207, 274], DSL (1) [207], OCL (1) [207]
	Model constraint generation (1)	OCL (1) [190], UML (1) [190]
	Model matching (1)	UML (1) [7]
	Model recognition (1)	UML (1) [34]
	Model restructuring (1)	UML (1) [109]
	Model synthesis (1)	UML (1) [180]
	Model transformation (1)	Rebeca (1) [166], UML (1) [166]
	Model view generation (1)	Ecore (1) [195], UML (1) [195]
	Model-based code evolution (1)	SysML v1 (1) [136]
2 Eclipse Modeling Framework (16)	Model generation (7)	Ecore (6) [194, 10, 193, 12, 33, 50], DSL (2) [10, 160], UML (2) [194, 12], OCL (1) [193], SysML v1 (1) [12]
	Model completion (4)	DSL (1) [71], Ecore (1) [259], UML (1) [38], Unspecified (1) [247]
	Model operation (2)	Ecore (2) [169, 168]
	Model constraint generation (1)	Ecore (1) [193], OCL (1) [193]
	Model mutation (1)	DSL (1) [87]
	Model view generation (1)	Ecore (1) [195], UML (1) [195]
	Model-based code evolution (1)	Ecore (1) [129]
	Model-based test generation (1)	Ecore (1) [193], OCL (1) [193]
3 Mermaid.js (5)	Model generation (4)	BPMN (2) [133, 134], DSL (2) [64, 105], UML (1) [105]
	Model comprehension (1)	DSL (1) [91]
4 PyEcore (3)	Model generation (1)	DSL (1) [10], Ecore (1) [10]
	Model mutation (1)	DSL (1) [87]
	Model view generation (1)	Ecore (1) [195], UML (1) [195]
5 TTool (2)	Model generation (2)	SysML v1 (2) [236, 17]
	Model analysis (1)	SysML v1 (1) [236]
6 bpmn.js (3)	Model generation (3)	BPMN (3) [182, 137, 62]
7 Cameo Systems Modeler (2)	Model generation (1)	SysML v1 (1) [252]
	Model query generation (1)	SysML v1 (1) [235]
8 Eclipse Capella (2)	Model generation (1)	DSL (1) [246]
	N/A (1)	N/A (1) [273]
9 Eclipse Sirius Editor (2)	Model completion (1)	UML (1) [38]
	Model generation (1)	Ecore (1) [12], SysML v1 (1) [12], UML (1) [12]
10 Graphviz (2)	Model generation (2)	BPMN (2) [153, 134]
11 HEPHYCODE (2)	Model operation (2)	Ecore (2) [169, 168]
12 Horus Business Modeler (2)	Model generation (1)	Petri Net (1) [214]
	Model transformation (1)	Petri Net (1) [94]
13 MORGAN [86] (2)	Model operation (2)	Ecore (2) [169, 168]
14 Modeling Event Recorder (MER) [83] (2)	Model operation (2)	Ecore (2) [169, 168]
15 Apache Jena Framework (1)	Model generation (1)	OWL (1) [74]
16 Apollon (1)	Model generation (1)	UML (1) [102]
17 BPMN Sketch Miner (1)	Model generation (1)	BPMN (1) [275]
18 CAEX (1)	Model operation (1)	Ecore (1) [168]
19 Camunda Modeler (1)	Model generation (1)	BPMN (1) [249]
20 Draw.io (1)	Model generation (1)	DSL (1) [121]
21 Eclipse Sirius Web (1)	Model generation (1)	DSL (1) [31]
22 FCA4J [110] (1)	Model restructuring (1)	UML (1) [109]
23 MOFM2T (1)	Model generation (1)	Ecore (1) [33]
24 Malva [29] (1)	Model-based code completion (1)	DSL (1) [52]
25 Matching Evaluation Toolkit (MELT) [120] (1)	Model matching (1)	DSL (1) [119]
26 MontiGEM [5] (1)	Model generation (1)	UML (1) [175]
27 PM4Py (1)	Model comprehension (1)	Petri Net (1) [41]
28 PlantText (1)	Model restructuring (1)	UML (1) [109]
29 ProcessPiper (1)	Model generation (1)	BPMN (1) [8]
30 Pydantic (1)	Model synthesis (1)	Declare (1) [75]
31 Qore-Base (1)	Model generation (1)	DSL (1) [250]
32 R-IOSUITE (1)	Model element extraction (1)	DSL (1) [68]
33 SiDiff Framework [215] (1)	Model completion (1)	Unspecified (1) [247]
34 Simulink (1)	Model slicing (1)	Simulink (1) [159]
35 S ³ checker [70] (1)	Model generation (1)	BPMN (1) [209]
36 Visual Paradigm (1)	Model comprehension (1)	UML (1) [18]
37 XModelerML (1)	Model restructuring (1)	FMMLx (1) [162]
38 [61] (1)	Model generation (1)	UML (1) [24]
39 [98] (1)	Model comprehension (1)	DSL (1) [99]
40 [104] (1)	Model generation (1)	DSL (1) [141]
41 [223] (1)	Model completion (1)	BPMN (1) [21]
42 vPAV [216] (1)	Model generation (1)	BPMN (1) [209]

Figure 12: Interaction patterns of human-in-the-loop of the LLM-based MDE solutions

lightweight and well-suited for rapid modeling, while EMF is comprehensive and has been the foundation of major open-source and commercial MDE tools such as Papyrus and MagicDraw. Both PlantUML and EMF have been widely adopted in industry and academia, and are supported by well-established communities. In addition, a wide range of other tools and frameworks has been adopted to support diverse MDE tasks, spanning from lightweight web-based tools (e.g., Mermaid.js and Draw.io) to heavy-duty industrial systems engineering suites (e.g., Simulink, Capella and Visual Paradigm).

We also notice that modeling languages manipulated in MDE tasks are strongly coupled with their supporting tools and platforms; for example, PlantUML is closely associated with UML and OCL, EMF-based environments primarily operate on Ecore models, and industrial platforms such as Cameo Systems Modeler are tightly aligned with SysML.

5.5 RQ12: In what ways are humans involved in the loop of LLM-based MDE solutions?

Answering this RQ is vital because, although MDE has historically aimed to reduce manual modeling through automation, the widespread adoption of LLMs introduces new challenges due to their inherent characteristics, such as randomness and hallucination. Consequently, recent studies have begun to emphasize the incorporation of human-in-the-loop (HITL) in LLM-based solutions. To better understand the roles of humans and the interaction patterns between humans and LLMs, Figure 12 presents the descriptive statistics of interactions patterns we observed.

Overall, in total, 24 studies propose LLM-based MDE solutions with explicit human involvement. Based on the interaction mechanisms reported in these studies, we identified four common HITL interaction patterns. The majority of studies (13) adopt feedback-based refinement, in which humans provide textual feedback or modification suggestions on generated artifacts (e.g., models or code), and the LLMs iteratively refines the results accordingly. Seven studies employ manual editing, where humans directly modify the generated artifacts without requiring further regeneration. Three studies adopt decision or selection-based interaction, in which humans choose among alternative candidates or suggestions generated by the LLMs, thereby determining subsequent activities. Notably, two studies adopt knowledge elicitation-based HITL approach, in which humans are engaged through interactive dialogue to answer clarifying questions generated by LLMs [214], or derived from pattern matches in the draft model [227], thereby soliciting feedback for refinement. Additionally, primary study [17] proposes an iterative approach combining feedback-based refinement and manual editing, where users have the choice to either provide extra knowledge or make manual corrections.

Key Finding on Proposed LLM-based MDE Solutions

GPT overwhelmingly dominates the primary studies, with other foundation models used far less frequently in a clear long-tail distribution. ZeroShot and FewShot are the most frequently applied single prompting techniques, and some effort has been made on experimenting hybrid prompting strategies. Only 28.1% of the primary studies employed enhancement techniques, with RAG and fine-tuning being the most commonly adopted. LLaMA and GPT are dominantly combined with fine-tuning and RAG. PlantUML and EMF are the most frequently used tools and frameworks, and a wide range of other tools and frameworks been adopted to support diverse MDE tasks as well. Humans are mostly involved to provide feedback on refining generated artifacts.

6 Evaluation Practices

This section presents the analysis of evaluation practices based on the comprehensive set of 228 primary studies.

6.1 RQ13: What metrics are used to evaluate the LLM-based MDE solutions?

It is important to investigate which metrics are used to evaluate models produced by LLM-based MDE solutions, as this is essential to assess whether and to what extent they truly outperform traditional approaches as claimed. To this end, we collected and summarize the cost and effectiveness metrics employed by the primary studies in Table 8 and Table 9, respectively.

6.1.1 Effectiveness Metrics

As shown in Table 8, we categorize effectiveness metrics into three classes: semantic only, syntactic only, and the both together. For each class, we further classify metrics according to their evaluation aspects (e.g., correctness and hallucination). Within each aspect, metrics are divided into quantitative and qualitative types. We consider that both quantitative and qualitative metrics can be either objective or subjective, and can additionally be categorized as reference-based (Ref-based) or reference-free (Ref-free), depending on whether a reference is required for comparison. In total, 123 primary studies adopt semantic effectiveness metrics. Among these, correctness is the most commonly used metric (101 studies), followed by completeness (56 studies), with 42 studies employing both correctness and completeness.

Semantic Metrics. Regarding semantic correctness, a diverse range of *objective--ref-based--quantitative* metrics is observed, e.g., accuracy, precision, and the number of correct models (in descending order of frequency), which constitute the most commonly adopted concrete metrics. In contrast, many other quantitative correctness metrics are used in four or fewer primary studies, such as model distance, and the percentage of acceptable models. When examining *subjective--ref-based--qualitative* correctness metrics, we observe that all primary studies use human rating. Specifically, the first category (i.e., *rating*) refers to a general assessment of semantic correctness, where evaluators directly rate how correct the generated output is. The second type, *reasonability rating* evaluates generated elements that are not present in the ground truth but could reasonably be included, capturing their plausibility and acceptability. The third type, *advanced feature rating*, assesses whether generated models go beyond basic entity and relationship structures to incorporate richer, domain-specific constructs. There is one metric, i.e., % of models conforming to semantic constraints, which is the only *objective--ref-free--quantitative* semantic correctness metric, which is interesting, as it does not rely on a reference model. However, it requires the explicit specification of semantic constraints as metamodel constraints or well-formedness constraints.

In terms of semantic completeness, among the 56 primary studies, the majority employs *objective--ref-based--quantitative* metrics, with recall as the dominant metric, followed by the percentage of covered elements and the number of missing elements. This is reasonable because semantic completeness inherently requires comparison against a reference to determine what elements should be present; therefore, objective, reference-based metrics such as recall naturally become the most appropriate and widely adopted measures. Similar to semantic correctness, some studies (7 out of 56) employ rating-based approaches to subjectively evaluate model quality, when reference models are available.

When evaluating model quality, correctness and completeness are naturally considered together. Accordingly, the F-measure is the most commonly used objective, reference-based, quantitative metric, followed by several variants such as Macro F1, soft F-measure, METEOR (Metric for Evaluation of Translation with Explicit ORdering), and METEOR@k, each of which appears in only one primary study. Rating is again the qualitative, subjective and reference-based metric observed in 2 out of 42 primary studies for evaluating the combined aspect of correctness and completeness.

Nine primary studies collect data on the counts and percentages of hallucinated elements, thereby forming objective, reference-based quantitative metrics. These elements are newly generated elements that are considered

irrelevant to the domain or system under study, hence indicating hallucinations of LLMs. In addition, subjective, reference-based qualitative metrics are also defined, including redundancy rating, relevance rating, and overall rating in the format of applying Likert scales to answer questions.

Measuring complexity is also important in evaluating the quality of models, as it reflects the structural characteristics and cognitive load associated with understanding and using the models [2]. As shown in Table 8, the first category comprises objective, reference-based quantitative metrics, including discrepancies in the number of elements, model size, and the number of unnecessary elements. The second category includes objective, reference-free quantitative metrics that do not require any reference models, such as size, density, separability, variability, and cohesion. The third category consists of subjective, reference-based qualitative metrics, in the form of human ratings with reference models available.

There are three primary studies cared by traceability. Specifically, in [246], traceability between generated design model elements and requirements was assessed manually using a Likert scale-based on a predefined rule set. The results were then aggregated to compute a mean traceability score for the entire generated architecture. In [72], traceability between model components and requirements was assessed using a scale-based approach by manually determining whether model components could be logically linked back to their originating requirements. Similarly, in [252], traceability of functions to logical elements was assessed by manually with a three-level scale: fully met, partially met, and not met.

Primary studies [246, 80] also apply objective, reference-based and quantitative metrics to measure granularity. In [246], the authors defined a specificity metric that leverages over specification and under specification parameters to identify if a generated architecture is more or less specific as compared to a pre-existing design architecture. For instance, if an element in the pre-existing model is aligned with multiple elements in a generated model, it is considered that the generated model is more specific, as the element in the pre-existing model could have been decomposed further to match the generated elements. Granularity variations [80] refer to differences in the level of detail when decomposing high-level activities into steps in business process analysis.

Human-centric metrics focus on evaluating model quality from the perspective of human model consumers. As shown in Table 8, nine primary studies adopt both subjective (objective), reference-based, qualitative (quantitative) metrics. Key aspects include understandability, ease of updating, simplicity, terminological alignment, clarity, pragmatics, and readability, among others.

Furthermore, six primary studies concern consistency. When references are available, similarity metrics or counts of inconsistencies were used to quantitatively measure consistency. Primary study [65] is the only one that focuses on measuring consistency of generated taxonomies against a set of rules, such as that each taxonomy can only have one root, which does not require references. Primary study [240] uses subjective rating to measure consistency, with references available.

Syntactic Metrics. In total, 42 studies employ syntactic metrics and as shown in Table 8, all of them concern syntactic correctness. In addition to reference-free or reference-based subjective and qualitative metrics such as rating, various quantitative metrics were employed. For reference-free ones, metrics include syntactic errors, correct outputs, success rates, etc. These metrics are mostly measured using tools for checking syntactic correctness against predefined rules or grammars, requiring no reference model. For reference-based approaches, metrics such as BLEU, Levenshtein distance, exact match, and accuracy were used, as these approaches define syntactic correctness in terms of alignment with a ground truth reference at different levels (e.g., n-gram overlap, edit distance, or exact correspondence), requiring a predefined reference for comparison.

Metrics Combining Both Semantic and Syntactic Aspects. We also observe primary studies that do not distinguish between semantics and syntax when evaluating models. These metrics are mostly about subjective rating of correctness, with or without references available. For quantitative metrics, when reference-free, primary study [9] measured adherence to UML syntactic and semantic constraints embedded within the prompt. In contrast, primary study [127] proposed XCORE to evaluate DSL queries through static analysis of syntax and semantics, as well as reference-based matching at the levels of sub-components and output schemas.

6.1.2 Cost metrics

Regarding cost metrics (Table 9), we distinguish between time cost and resource cost. Specifically, 33 primary studies report time-related metrics, while 13 report resource-related metrics. Notice that there are primary studies (i.e., [96, 193, 19, 184, 154, 6]) that report both types of metrics.

For time cost, 33 primary studies evaluate their approaches using a range of metrics, which we group into three categories: (1) training effort, i.e., the time required to train or fine-tune LLMs; (2) inference/generation time, i.e., the runtime needed to produce artifacts or responses; and (3) total task duration, i.e., the end-to-end time required to complete the task. As shown in the table, 21 studies report total task duration, while 14 out of 33 report inference/generation time. Only three studies report training effort. We also observe that a small number of primary studies (i.e., [96, 169, 168, 73]) report both total task duration and inference/generation time, which we consider a good practice for empirical evaluation.

Table 8: Effectiveness metrics applied in the primary studies to assess LLM-based MDE solutions

Category	Aspect	Papers									
Semantic (123)	Correctness (101)	<p>Quantitative (Objective, Ref-based): Accuracy [84, 249, 132, 71, 159, 3, 254, 161, 64, 62, 141], Precision [224, 115, 246, 55, 258, 135, 226, 178, 196, 169, 265, 8, 44, 106, 66, 65, 59, 30, 152, 36, 108, 134, 168, 57, 79, 203, 225, 227, 24, 191, 157, 151, 62], # of correct models [115, 127, 42, 133], # of correct elements [194, 166, 127, 33, 272, 238, 233], # of neutral additional elements [166], # of enhanced elements [166], # of misplaced elements [166], % of correct models [182, 156, 4], # of incorrect elements [78, 272, 276, 14], Model distance [78, 154], % of acceptable models [156], % of incorrect models [156], Pass@k [156], MRR@k [71], Success rate@k [71], Cosine similarity [190, 3, 228, 187, 218, 22], Euclidean distance [190, 102], Graph edit distance [153], Alignment score [250], # of incorrect models [42], Recall@k [259, 32], MRR [259], Precision@k [32], F-measure@k [32], MMR (Maximal Marginal Relevance adjusted) [32], NDCGp (Normalized Discounted Cumulative Gain at p) [32], # of relevant additional elements [33, 238], # of out-of-scope additional elements [33], Footprint-based fitness [200], % of correct elements [80, 63, 38, 260, 13], % of incorrect elements [80, 63], % of relevant additional elements [63], Cosine similarity@k [229], TEDS (Tree-Edit-Distance-based Similarity) [203], MAP@k [25], ET-Conformance precision [140], # of unsatisfied requirements [191], Structural similarity [202], Behavioral similarity [202], BERTScore [50], Soft precision [64]</p> <p>Qualitative (Subjective, Ref-based): Rating [40, 185, 175, 126, 72, 92, 138, 252, 17, 81, 121, 134, 137, 149, 214, 184, 154, 209, 220, 212, 231, 240, 26], Reasonability rating [228, 187, 218], Advanced features rating [26]</p>									
		Completeness (56)	<p>Quantitative (Objective, Ref-free): % of models conforming to semantic constraints [209, 64]</p> <p>Quantitative (Objective, Ref-based): Recall [224, 115, 246, 55, 258, 226, 178, 196, 169, 265, 8, 44, 106, 66, 65, 59, 30, 152, 36, 108, 134, 168, 57, 79, 203, 225, 227, 24, 191, 157, 151, 62], % of covered elements [101, 135, 63, 260, 9], # of missing elements [166, 239, 33, 238, 276, 189, 14], # of covered elements [72, 206], Richness [21], Jaccard similarity [134], Token-based fitness [140], Soft recall [64]</p> <p>Qualitative (Subjective, Ref-based): Rating [185, 92, 81, 121, 184, 209, 26]</p>								
			Correctness + Completeness (42)	<p>Quantitative (Objective, Ref-based): F-measure [224, 115, 46, 55, 198, 258, 226, 178, 196, 169, 265, 45, 8, 44, 106, 66, 19, 65, 30, 36, 108, 204, 168, 57, 16, 25, 225, 227, 24, 220, 256, 191, 157, 151, 62], METEOR [127], Macro F1 [199, 200], METEOR@k [229], Soft F-measure [64]</p> <p>Qualitative (Subjective, Ref-based): Rating [201, 253]</p>							
				Hallucination (14)	<p>Quantitative (Objective, Ref-based): % of hallucinated elements [101, 210, 256], # of hallucinated elements [46, 33, 238, 276, 189, 14]</p> <p>Qualitative (Subjective, Ref-based): Redundancy rating [201], Relevance rating [185, 184, 209], Rating [240]</p>						
					Complexity (11)	<p>Quantitative (Objective, Ref-based): Discrepancy in # of elements [239], Size [159], # of unnecessary elements [31, 276]</p> <p>Quantitative (Objective, Ref-free): Size [75], Density [75], Separability [75], Variability [75], # of specific elements [143, 222, 184, 31], Contribution rate [38], Overlap coefficient [38], Cohesion [13]</p> <p>Qualitative (Subjective, Ref-based): Rating [252]</p>					
						Traceability (3)	<p>Qualitative (Subjective, Ref-based): Rating [246, 72, 252]</p>				
							Granularity (2)	<p>Quantitative (Objective, Ref-based): Specificity [246], % of granularity variations [80]</p>			
								Human-centric (9)	<p>Qualitative (Subjective, Ref-based): Understandability rating [185, 92, 184], Ease of updating rating [185, 184], Simplicity rating [72], Terminological alignment rating [92], Clarity rating [81], Pragmatic rating [149], Readability rating [260]</p> <p>Quantitative (Objective, Ref-based): # of pragmatic errors [78], # of preserved auxiliary elements [272], # of missing auxiliary elements [272], Clarity rate [260]</p>		
									Consistency (6)	<p>Quantitative (Objective, Ref-based): Cosine similarity [175], # of inconsistencies [236], Jaccard similarity [233]</p> <p>Qualitative (Subjective, Ref-based): Rating [72, 240]</p>	
										Syntactic (42)	Correctness (42)
Sem+Syn (3)	Correctness (3)										

Table 9: Cost metrics applied in the primary studies to assess LLM-based MDE solutions

Category	Metrics	Papers
Time (33)	Total task duration (21)	[136, 182, 198, 96, 169, 114, 72, 17, 19, 81, 144, 119, 168, 107, 184, 38, 154, 73, 191, 6, 89]
	Inference/generation time (14)	[23, 53, 96, 169, 71, 193, 192, 176, 168, 73, 140, 256, 240, 34]
	Training effort (3)	[199, 200, 34]
	Token consumption (10)	[7, 246, 185, 28, 96, 193, 138, 137, 184, 6]
Resource (15)	Monetary cost (6)	[84, 100, 246, 96, 19, 154]
	API overhead (1)	[254]
Total _{time}	33	14.47%
Total _{resource}	15	6.58%

Regarding resource-related cost metrics, we categorize them into three types: (1) token consumption, representing the number of tokens consumed during prompt processing and response generation (e.g., total tokens or average tokens per artifact); (2) monetary cost, referring to the financial expenses associated with using LLM services or computational infrastructure; and (3) API overhead, referring to the number or frequency of API invocations required to complete a task. Among these types, token consumption is the most frequently used metric.

6.2 RQ14: What baselines were used to assess LLM-based MDE solutions?

It is essential to explicitly report the baselines used when evaluating LLM-based MDE solutions, as only rigorous comparison against established state-of-the-art approaches can substantiate claimed advancement. To this end, we summarize the types of the baselines employed by the primary studies in Figure 13.

Overall, only 59 out of 228 primary studies involve baseline methods for evaluation. The baselines can be broadly categorized into rule-based approaches, which rely on predefined rules or prior knowledge, and data-driven approaches, which leverage statistical and machine learning models to learn increasingly complex patterns and representations from data, including traditional machine learning, deep learning, and LLM-based methods, with training data scale, model size, and architectural complexity progressively increasing, while interpretability correspondingly decreases [60].

Figure 13 indicates that LLM-based MDE solutions are most frequently compared against data-driven approaches. Among these, comparisons with other LLM-based approaches are the most common (41 studies), including direct prompting of LLMs (e.g., [191] uses GPT-o3 as a baseline LLM against the proposed MAL-LLM for developing Meta Attack Language) and existing LLM-based pipelines (e.g., [182] compared its method with ProMoAI [139] for BPMN process model generation), followed by deep learning approaches (6 studies, e.g., [222] is evaluated against an LSTM-based method [221] and shown to be effective in the synthesis of Simulink models) and traditional machine learning approaches (3 studies, e.g., [108] is compared with a SVM-based method [124] for extracting use case models from given requirements). In contrast, comparatively fewer studies benchmark them against more foundational rule-based baselines (15 studies, e.g., [46] compared its LLM-based solution with a rule-based NLP method, Visual Narrator [205], for deriving domain models). In addition, a small number of papers adopt alternative baselines, including hybrid approaches (i.e., a model transformation method [148] combining ML and predefined rules, as used in [7], and a process model generation method [177] combining traditional ML and deep learning, as adopted in [178]) and search-based techniques (i.e., a test scenario fuzzing approach, LawBreaker [237], as used in [84], and a metamodel matching method [131], as adopted in [7]), which can also serve as meaningful reference points for evaluation; while a few studies (2) rely on random or trivial baselines for comparison.

6.3 RQ15: What public replication artifacts do the primary studies provide?

Although replication packages are strongly encouraged to promote transparency and reproducibility, they are not consistently available; therefore, in this survey, we systematically collected available replication packages to facilitate knowledge sharing and reuse within the community.

In total, only 119 out of 228 primary studies come with replication materials that share at least one of the four types of artifacts: evaluated subject, source code, prompt and enhanced-LLMs. When looking into details, as shown in Figure 14, 92 primary studies provide materials of their evaluated subjects (e.g., case studies or benchmarks), 57 release source code, and 55 make prompts available. Only five out of 43 primary studies that employed enhancement techniques (see Section 5.3) provide their enhanced-LLMs available. We further examined the primary studies to get an idea whether an evaluated subject belongs to industry. Results reveal that the industry vs. non-industry proportion is roughly 1 : 8.7. This clearly indicates that current evaluations

Figure 13: Bar chart presenting the distribution of types of baselines employed by the primary studies

Table 10: Replicable artifacts made available in the primary studies

Artifacts	#	Papers
Prompt + Evaluation Subject + Source Code	13	[55, 40, 195, 265, 165, 66, 254, 80, 204, 272, 247, 25, 6]
Enhanced-LLM + Evaluation Subject + Source Code	3	[259, 16, 156]
Prompt + Enhanced-LLM + Evaluation Subject	1	[39]
Prompt + Evaluation Subject	25	[46, 111, 11, 45, 230, 138, 4, 81, 3, 56, 133, 36, 108, 137, 93, 79, 238, 208, 225, 102, 240, 109, 162, 14, 167]
Evaluation Subject + Source Code	23	[84, 75, 226, 196, 129, 71, 126, 236, 199, 200, 63, 214, 38, 187, 227, 154, 112, 157, 64, 22, 99, 189, 141]
Prompt + Source Code	7	[269, 178, 169, 48, 168, 57, 218]
Enhanced-LLM + Source Code	1	[53]
Evaluation Subject	27	[224, 101, 166, 78, 49, 253, 190, 153, 44, 139, 21, 15, 17, 244, 30, 121, 176, 134, 41, 206, 20, 145, 161, 140, 256, 188, 34]
Source Code	10	[10, 147, 158, 59, 222, 229, 74, 26, 89, 13]
Prompt	9	[210, 248, 106, 142, 94, 228, 231, 202, 62]

of LLM-based MDE solutions are predominantly conducted in controlled, academic settings, which may limit external validity, industrial realism, and scalability assessment.

As shown in Table 10, not all primary studies provide a comprehensive set of replication materials. For instance, only $13+3=17$ primary studies (out of 119) provide source code, in addition to evaluation subjects and either prompts or enhanced-LLMs. Less comprehensively, 25 make both prompts and evaluation subjects available, and 23 reveal the employed evaluation subjects and meanwhile provide source code. For the rest, the majority only provide evaluation subjects.

We further provide a comprehensive list of hyperlinks for all replicable artifacts available in Table 11 to foster a culture of transparency within the research community.

Key Finding on Evaluation Practices

Current evaluations of the effectiveness of LLM-based MDE solutions rely on a diverse set of metrics, which can be broadly categorized into semantic and syntactic dimensions. Among these, correctness is the primary focus, alongside other aspects such as completeness, hallucination, and complexity. Time and resource costs are also considered in some primary studies, although more fine-grained time-related metrics are still needed. LLMs are commonly used as baselines when assessing proposed LLM-based MDE approaches. However, existing benchmarks are largely confined to controlled academic settings, and there is a notable lack of transparency and publicly available replication materials.

Table 11: Summary of available artifacts provided for replication and evaluation

Paper	Source Code	Prompt	Enhanced-LLM	Evaluation Subject	Paper	Source Code	Prompt	Enhanced-LLM	Evaluation Subject
[55]	GitHub	osf.io		GitHub	[64]	GitHub			GitHub
[40]	GitHub	GitHub		GitHub	[22]	GitHub			huggingface
[195]	Zenodo	Zenodo		Zenodo	[99]	doi.org			doi.org
[265]	GitHub	GitHub		GitHub	[189]	Zenodo			Zenodo
[165]	GitHub	GitHub		GitHub	[141]	Zenodo			Zenodo
[66]	Zenodo	Zenodo		Zenodo	[269]	GitHub	GitHub		
[254]	GitHub	Appendix		GitHub	[178]	GitHub	GitHub		
[80]	GitHub	GitHub		GitHub	[169]	GitHub	GitHub		
[204]	GitHub	GitHub		GitHub	[48]	GitHub	GitHub		
[272]	osf.io	osf.io		osf.io	[168]	GitHub	Figshare		
[247]	GitHub	Appendix		GitHub	[57]	Figshare	Figshare		
[25]	GitHub	GitHub		GitHub	[218]	GitHub	GitHub		
[6]	GitHub	GitHub		GitHub	[53]	GitHub		huggingface	
[259]	GitHub		doi.org	doi.org	[224]				Zenodo
[16]	GitHub		huggingface	GitHub	[101]				Figshare
[156]	Zenodo		huggingface	huggingface	[166]				GitHub
[39]		Zenodo	huggingface	Zenodo	[78]				doi.org
[46]		Zenodo	huggingface	Zenodo	[49]				GitHub
[111]		Zenodo		Zenodo	[253]				Zenodo
[11]		Zenodo		Zenodo	[190]				huggingface
[45]		Zenodo		Zenodo	[153]				Appendix
[230]		Zenodo		Zenodo	[44]				ieee-dataport.org
[138]		GitHub		GitHub	[139]				GitHub
[4]		Zenodo		Zenodo	[21]				GitHub
[81]		GitHub		GitHub	[15]				Zenodo
[3]		Zenodo		Zenodo	[17]				GitHub
[56]		GitHub		GitHub	[244]				huggingface
[133]		GitHub		GitHub	[30]				Appendix
[36]		pdi.fbk.eu		pdi.fbk.eu	[121]				GitHub
[108]		GitLab		GitLab	[176]				GitHub
[137]		GitHub		GitHub	[134]				huggingface , Zenodo
[93]		Appendix		Appendix	[41]				data.4tu.nl 1 , data.4tu.nl 2 , data.4tu.nl 3 , data.4tu.nl 4
[79]		Google-Doc		tinyurl.com	[206]				re4cps.org
[238]		GitHub		GitHub	[20]				GitHub
[208]		GitHub		GitHub	[145]				Appendix
[225]		Zenodo		Zenodo	[161]				europa.eu 1 , europa.eu 2 , europa.eu 3
[102]		doi.org		doi.org	[140]				GitHub
[240]		GitHub		GitHub	[256]				Google-Drive
[109]		gite.lirmm.fr		gite.lirmm.fr	[188]				Zenodo
[162]		wi-inf.uni-due.de		wi-inf.uni-due.de	[34]				Zenodo
[14]		tinyurl.com		tinyurl.com	[10]	GitHub			
[167]		Zenodo		Zenodo	[147]	GitHub			
[84]	Zenodo			Google-Doc	[158]	diavio.github.io			
[75]	GitHub			GitHub	[59]	GitHub			
[226]	GitHub			GitHub	[222]	Zenodo			
[196]	GitHub			GitHub	[229]	GitHub			
[129]	Figshare			Figshare	[74]	GitHub			
[71]	GitHub			GitHub	[26]	GitHub			
[126]	GitHub			GitHub	[89]	GitHub			
[236]	GitLab			Zenodo	[13]	GitHub			
[199]	GitHub			Zenodo	[210]		GitHub		
[200]	GitHub			Zenodo	[248]		GitHub		
[63]	GitHub			GitHub	[106]		GitHub		
[214]	GitHub			huggingface	[142]		Appendix		
[38]	GitHub 1 , GitHub 2			GitHub	[94]		GitHub		
[187]	Figshare			Figshare	[228]		Appendix		
[227]	GitHub			GitHub	[231]		Zenodo		
[154]	4open.science			GitHub , omg.org	[202]		GitHub		
[112]	Zenodo			Zenodo	[62]		tinyurl.com		
[157]	GitHub			GitHub					

Figure 14: Bar chart representing the distribution of types of artifacts made available as replication materials

7 Threats To Validity

Construct Validity. A key threat is whether the search strategy and data extraction accurately reflect the constructs behind the 15 RQs. We derived and iteratively refined search strings based on the RQs and defined detailed extraction and coding guidelines. Nevertheless, heterogeneous terminologies and the interpretation of abstract concepts may have led to under representation or classification bias. To enhance rigor and replicability, we followed a well-established SLR methodology and made the protocol and procedures transparent. The artifacts of our SLR are available at <https://github.com/WSE-Lab/LLM4MDE>.

Internal Validity. Bias may arise in study selection, quality assessment, and coding. Although inclusion and exclusion criteria were pre-defined and applied systematically, subjective judgment in borderline cases may have affected the final set of the 228 primary studies. Multiple authors cross-checked results and resolved disagreements through consensus, but residual bias cannot be fully eliminated.

External Validity. The generalizability of the findings depends on the coverage of the included studies. Despite querying multiple digital libraries and applying snowballing, some relevant or non-English studies may have been missed. In addition, given the rapid growth of research on LLMs in MDE, new studies may have emerged during the review process. Nonetheless, the large dataset and systematic procedure support the representativeness of the reported results.

Conclusion Validity. The reliability of the synthesized observations depends on accurate extraction and aggregation. Although we applied systematic synthesis and maintained traceability from results to primary studies, interpretation and aggregation bias may still exist.

8 Related Work

With the rapid development of LLMs, traditional MDE paradigms are being fundamentally reshaped, which drives a significant shift in how MDE tasks are performed. In this evolving landscape, an increasing number of studies have examined how MDE, as well as broader SE activities, integrate with emerging AI technologies.

Surveys on LLMs for SE. Several works have surveyed the application of LLMs in the SE context. For instance, Fan et al. [90] conducted a comprehensive survey on the application of LLMs across the spectrum of SE activities, encompassing requirements, design, coding, repair, refactoring, performance improvement, documentation and analytics. Their work highlights the dominance of code-centric tasks, while explicitly noting that higher-level activities like LLM-based requirement engineering or design remain under-explored. Hou et al. [122] conducted an SLR on understanding how LLMs can be applied to perform SE tasks. The authors examined types of adopted LLMs and their characteristics, analyzed data collection, preprocessing, and application practices, and discussed approaches for optimizing and evaluating LLMs’ performance. In addition, the study reviews SE tasks where LLMs have been successfully applied, with a primary focus on software development, quality assurance, and maintenance. He et al. [116] reviewed the research landscape on integrating LLMs into Multi-Agent (LMA) systems for addressing challenges in SE across different stages of the software development lifecycle. Their work highlights recent advances in areas such as requirements engineering, code

generation, quality assurance, maintenance, and further proposes a structured research agenda to advance LMA integration in SE.

Although these studies provide valuable insights into how LLMs are integrated into SE activities, they primarily focus on LLMs in SE, in general, with a strong emphasis on code-centric tasks. In contrast, our study focuses on the use of LLMs within MDE, emphasizing the central role of high-level abstractions captured in knowledge models (e.g., meta-models, domain models, and DSLs). Accordingly, we investigate how LLMs are utilized in MDE tasks and how these solutions are evaluated, etc. by providing a fine-grained examination and comprehension of the LLM-based MDE solution landscape.

Surveys on LLMs for MDE. Within the MDE community, there has also been research exploring the integration of AI techniques with MDE. For instance, Marcén et al. [163] conducted a SLR of MDE using machine learning techniques, covering studies up to 2023 and analyzing 98 primary studies. The review discussed the trend in the usage of different ML techniques, model characteristics, dataset availability, the maturity of ML-based solutions and remaining research challenges. Additionally, the review highlights that while current research primarily focuses on neural networks, it is reasonable to expect increased exploration of LLMs for solving MDE problems in future studies. Burgueno et al. [51] discussed the opportunities and challenges of integrating MDE with AI. They highlight that, while the advent of LLMs further enables the automation of modeling tasks, the MDE research community has not yet fully capitalized the potential of AI, particularly deep learning and LLMs, due to several inherent challenges, including the scarcity of MDE-specific datasets, the diversity and structural complexity of artifacts, and the difficulty of crafting effective prompts. Storey et al. [234] discussed the current and potential role of LLMs in conceptual modeling, presenting the state of art based on 9 primary studies. They further examined the potential impacts and risks of LLMs and demonstrated their applicability through a concrete example of identifying data models across three tasks and two datasets, while also discussing how the conceptual modeling community might adopt them. Fresemann et al. [95] conducted a literature review on the use of LLMs to support system modeling, and identified 20 relevant publications. They analyzed the technical setup of LLM-based solutions, their evaluation strategies, as well as existing gaps and limitations. Di Rocco et al. [85] presented an overview of LLM applications in MDE. They selected 14 papers published between January 2019 and July 2024, analyzing LLM-based solutions in MDE tasks including model completion, model search, model generation, model management operations, model architecture, DSL requirements, and goal modeling. The study also proposes a research agenda, identifying key challenges and opportunities for leveraging LLMs in MDE and vice versa.

Surveys on MDE for AI. In addition, several studies have investigated the use of MDE for AI. Naveed et al. [174] explored a range of MDE solutions applied to ML systems, including modeling languages, model transformations, tool support, and targeted ML aspects. Rädler et al. [197] investigated the use of DSLs for engineering AI software systems. Their study highlights that the application of MDE for AI is still in its early stages and proposed several research directions to guide future work.

Compared to existing studies within the MDE community, we conduct the first SLR on the use of LLMs in MDE, covering 228 primary studies published between 2017 and October 2025. Our review provides a comprehensive analysis by covering a broader range of MDE tasks, modeling languages, model types, and techniques in terms of how LLMs are leveraged and enhanced in MDE solutions, as well as human involvement patterns. In addition, we place particular emphasis on evaluation practices in current research by systematically summarizing cost-effectiveness metrics, the types of baselines adopted for evaluation, and publicly available replication artifacts, with the aim of facilitating and supporting future work in the field.

9 Conclusion

In this systematic literature review (SLR), we assessed the extent to which LLMs are reshaping Model-Driven Engineering (MDE) and the maturity of the emerging research landscape. Across 228 primary studies, we observe a rapidly expanding body of work spanning a broad spectrum of MDE tasks, with a clear concentration on model generation and related automation scenarios, while other phases of the MDE lifecycle remain comparatively underexplored. Despite promising indications of improved productivity and accessibility, current evidence is constrained by heterogeneous and often limited evaluation practices. Most studies focus on correctness in controlled settings, with scarce use of realistic industrial datasets, limited reproducibility, and a lack of standardized benchmarks. As a result, the practical impact and generalizability of existing approaches remain uncertain.

Looking forward, a central challenge is to develop a principled understanding of how to effectively harness LLMs for performing MDE tasks. This requires moving beyond ad hoc applications toward systematic approaches that align LLM capabilities with the abstractions, constraints, and formalisms inherent in MDE. In parallel, an equally promising but less explored direction is the use of MDE itself to structure, constrain, and engineer LLM-based systems, thereby improving their reliability, interpretability, and integration into complex system development processes. Ultimately, while LLMs show strong potential as enablers of automation and accessibility

in MDE, their transformative impact will depend on methodological maturation and principled integration. Models will remain central artifacts, providing the necessary abstraction, structure, and analyzability required for engineering complex software-intensive systems. For replicability and reproducibility, we have the artifacts of our SLR available at <https://github.com/WSE-Lab/LLM4MDE>.

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